

HISTORY AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8415783>

Plato, Heraclitus, Saint-Simon, O. Comte, G.V. Plekhanov, P.A. Sorokin, E. Durkheim, M. Weber and others represent a far from complete series of outstanding thinkers and scientists who studied the problems of the existence and development of various social systems. Why do some consider them social philosophers, others sociologists, others political scientists, others consider them theorists of social and general psychology, etc. Why in the “West” is there no clear division of areas of scientific interests of social philosophers, sociologists, political scientists, and social psychologists.

An attempt to answer these questions leads, firstly, to the need to state the following facts: a really existing society at a specific point in time has one real life, determined by its past; all social sciences have one object of study - society (from man in it to society “in general”); all social sciences study “active man”, that is, it is considered as a system “man - his activity - living conditions”; the presence in any more or less organized society, community, group of people of a social division of labor.

Secondly, to the definition of the main components of social activity through their purpose in the social division of labor: the economic component - production, exchange and distribution of goods as products of human labor, ensuring the existence and development of man and society as a whole; social - production and reproduction of connections, relationships between people, consumption of goods and values, that is, reproduction of the life of society and human social life; political - regulation (management) of a really existing society, processes and relationships occurring in it; spiritual - production and reproduction of values (selection, storage and distribution of goods that have a positive significance for the existence and development of man and society as a whole).

Thirdly, to the concept of the formation and development of science, scientific knowledge in the form of judgment: from living contemplation to abstract thinking and from it to practice, this is the path to knowledge of truth, knowledge of objective reality. In the system of scientific knowledge, theories occupy an important place as meaningful, systematized knowledge about objective reality. Theories become scientific as a result of verification by human practice, which is a material, sensory-objective, goal-setting activity of people, which has as its content the development and transformation of natural and

social objects and constitutes the universal basis, the driving force for the development of human society and human cognition. In the process of this activity, research is carried out on social reality and the collection of objective information about it. The acquired knowledge is used by people in practice, existing theories are tested.

Science is based on proven theories and exists as a system of knowledge that has been tested or can be tested by practice. The impact of people on social reality consists of: the reproduction of existing and the production of new relationships between specific members of society and existing social objects; in organizing the interaction of new relationships with existing ones; in optimization and institutionalization (consolidation in norms, etc.) of interaction of relations.

At the same time, the institutionalization of scientific knowledge occurs on the basis of compliance with the “levels” of human allocation in the environment (nature) and social organization to the social division of labor.

Fourthly, to the concept of “impact on reality” in the following main directions: through the preservation of existing social relations (conservative direction); through changing existing social relations, creating new ones (progressive or regressive direction); along the main paths: a) evolutionary; b) revolutionary (counter-revolutionary).

We consider everything that exists, existence itself, in relation to ourselves, representing its unity of existence of man and his environment (nature); regarding our consciousness, representing it as the unity of the existence of objective and subjective realities; regarding our sensations through the senses, representing it as the unity of the existence of material and ideal realities. The whole history can be viewed from two sides, in it one can distinguish the history of nature (the history of natural science) and the history of people (the history of social science), while taking the position of either materialism or idealism, or objectivism or subjectivism.

The materialist understanding of history proceeds from real premises that are not arbitrary and are not dogmas from which one can abstract only in the imagination. It proceeds from the fact that these are actual individuals, their activities and the conditions of their lives, both those that they find ready-made and those that are created by their own activity.

The first premise of every human society, of every human history, is, of course, the existence of living human individuals.

Secondly, people begin to distinguish themselves from animals as soon as they begin to produce the means of life they need. By producing the means of life they need, people produce their very material social life. This method of production must be considered as a certain way of activity of specific people, a certain type of their life activity, their certain way of life.

Thirdly, specific individuals engaged in real production activities enter into certain economic, social, spiritual and political relationships. The connection of economic, social and political structures with the production of goods and values, social structure and the state constantly arise from the life process of certain people. People are constantly in constant production relations with each other, during which they produce: goods necessary for their existence and development (economic relations of production), values, that is, everything that has a positive meaning for its existence and development (spiritual relations of production), connections, relationships among themselves (social production relations), that is, the life of society and the social life of a person, the sequence of exchange and consumption of goods and values, the implementation of social connections and relationships (political relations of production), that is, the regulation and management of social relations.

Society is the result of the practical activities of people, but this very activity is determined by the conditions in which people find themselves, the means of production, knowledge, skills, abilities already acquired earlier, the social form of production relations that existed before them, which was created not by these people, but by previous ones generations.

Thus, the history of society, the sociocultural development of society is nothing more than a successive succession of individual generations, each of which uses the productive forces and production relations transmitted to it by previous generations. In order to understand a specific society, its genesis, it is necessary, based on the material production of immediate life, to consider the actual process of production and understand the form of social relations generated by it (that is, civil society as the basis of development), then depict the activities of civil society in the sphere of political and state life, explain from this various theoretical creations and forms of social consciousness and trace the process of their emergence. Thanks to this, it will be possible to present the entire process as a whole, as well as the relationships and interactions between its various parties.

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